

The Future of Automotive Production in Europe: Transformation and Challenges at SEAT S.A.

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Abstract

The automotive sector in Europe is facing the most challenging transformation and disruption in decades. The electrification of the vehicle portfolio, alongside the digitalization of manufacturing processes are key factors in this transformation. Identifying challenges and opportunities related to new technological trends, environmental sustainability, the demand of new markets and supply chain efficiencies is essential to maintain industrial competitiveness.

The Spanish car manufacturer SEAT S.A., with its two complementary brands SEAT and CUPRA, is undergoing the largest industrial, organizational, and cultural transformation in its 74-year history as it shifts from combustion to electric vehicles. Electrification is SEAT S.A.'s opportunity to lead the future. 70 years ago, SEAT put Spain on wheels and now the company is putting the country on electric wheels. With operations in over 70 countries and exporting more than 80% of its vehicles, SEAT S.A. is contributing to Spain's role as a major player in the automotive industry. The country is the second largest car manufacturer in Europe and the 8th biggest worldwide. The company's ambitious Future: Fast Forward project, in collaboration with the Volkswagen Group and PowerCo, aims to establish Spain as a European hub for electromobility through a €10 billion investment, which includes the electrification of its Martorell and Pamplona factories and the construction of Spain's first gigafactory.

SEAT, S.A. as part of the Volkswagen Group, one of the biggest automotive groups in Europe, is a clear example of how transformational challenges can be effectively addressed. The transformation of the company is affecting its three production centres: Martorell, El Prat de Llobregat and Barcelona. These are being transformed into the factory of the future with agile, networked, and optimized production and supply chains. This transformation is characterized by integrating advanced technologies, digitalization, data processing and improved logistics and a connected and agile supply chain to optimize production.

In the area of digitalization, artificial intelligence is increasingly becoming a key driver, making companies more productive, efficient, and sustainable. At SEAT S.A., it is utilized in areas such as supply chain optimization, predictive maintenance, quality control, and defect detection. An important aspect of the company's transition involves the upskilling the workforce to prepare them for the future through the most ambitious training plan in the company's history, encouraging a winning mentality and an openness to change.

The company works in guaranteeing the long-term sustainability of its business, which will be key in a highly competitive global market. Through the Volkswagen Group and its multi-brand strategy, SEAT S.A. shares resources to implement Smart Production across all its facilities, positioning the company in pole position to lead electromobility across Europe.

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